

Medium Effects on Activation Parameters of Alkaline Hydrolysis of Monomethylsuccinate Ion

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The effect of the solvent on the activation parameters for the reaction between monomethylsuccinate and hydroxide ions has been studied by using water, 20% ethanol-water and 20% ethylene glycol-water. Two sets of isodielectric ethanol-water mixtures of dielectric constants 68.66 and 50.38 and one set of isodielectric ethylene glycol-water mixtures of dielectric constant 68.66 have been used. The activation parameters have been dissected into the electrostatic and nonelectrostatic components. An analysis of the activation energy, entropy of activation and nonelectrostatic potential reveals that solvation of the transition state is larger in ethanol-water than in ethylene glycol-water of the same dielectric constant. The free energy of activation for the isodielectric (68.66) ethanol-water has a much lower positive value than for the corresponding isodielectric glycol-water medium, implying poor compensation between ΔH^\ddagger and $T\Delta S^\ddagger$, as well as structural differences between the two solvent systems.

ATTEMPTS have been made to correlate the medium effects on the activation parameters of ion-ion reactions on the basis of electrostatic factors, but much about these effects remains obscure. The progress in this field has been summarised by several authors¹⁻³. We had earlier⁴ reported ion-association and specific solvent effects on the rates of alkaline hydrolysis of monomethyl succinate ion, which is a reaction between two anions. This reaction has now been studied in mixed media to obtain the activation parameters, which have been dissected into electrostatic and non-electrostatic components to obtain an insight into the state of the activated complex in the different media.

Experimental

The experimental procedure was the same as described earlier⁴. Rates have been measured in 20% (w/w) ethanol-water and 20% (w/w) ethylene glycol-water mixtures. Two sets of isodielectric ethanol-water mixtures of dielectric constants (D) 68.66 and 50.38, and one set of isodielectric ethylene

glycol-water mixtures of dielectric constant 68.66 have also been used. Rates in each solvent medium have been measured at three temperatures (20, 30, 40°) and at four ionic strengths (I) in the range 0.02 to 0.11 M, keeping the initial concentration of each of the reactants at 0.01 M. The ionic strengths were varied by adding calculated amounts of standard sodium chloride solution. The second order rate constants (k_0) at zero ionic strength, obtained from the linear plots of $\log k$ against \sqrt{I} with extrapolation to zero ionic strength, are reported in Table 1. The rate constants are found to be reproducible within $\pm 2\%$. The activation energy, the Arrhenius frequency factor (A), the entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) and the free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) in the different media have been calculated in the usual way. Experimental values of activation energies (E_0) at zero ionic strength for the different media are reported in Table 2.

Results and Discussions

Activation energies :

If a medium of constant composition is

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS (k_0 , $l. \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) IN DIFFERENT MEDIA AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	Water		20% Ethanol-water		20% Ethylene glycol-water	
	Dielectric constant	k_0	Dielectric constant	k_0	Dielectric constant	k_0
20	80.37	2.85	68.66	2.08	74.60	1.6
30	76.76	5.62	65.31	4.31	71.04	3.0
40	73.12	10.72	62.41	8.91	67.52	6.5

Temp. °C	Ethylene glycol (% w/w)		Ethanol (% w/w)		Ethanol (% w/w)	
	Dielectric constant	k_0	Dielectric constant	k_0	Dielectric constant	k_0
20	40	0.95	20	2.08	50	1.17
30	27.8	2.50	14	4.36	45.6	2.66
40	15.6	6.90	8.4	10.12	41.2	6.30

TABLE 2—EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF ACTIVATION ENERGY (E_0 , cal./mole) AT ZERO IONIC STRENGTH FOR DIFFERENT COMPOSITIONS OF ETHYLENE GLYCOL-WATER AND ETHANOL-WATER

% Organic solvent (w/w)	E_0	
	ethanol-water	ethylene glycol-water
10	12561	13050
20	12666	13472
30	13819	14323
40	15510	15833
50	15911	16343
60	16450	16842

used at different temperatures, the dielectric constant varies with temperature and hence the measured temperature coefficient of the rate constant includes not only the increased energy of the reactants due to pure thermal effects, but also the changed electrical forces due to changes in the dielectric constant of the solvent. However, if the temperature coefficient of the rate of a reaction between two ions is measured in two sets of isodielectric media comprising the same solvent pair, the difference in the reaction rate should depend to a large extent on the difference in the electrostatic forces between the reactants in the two dielectrics and the difference in temperature coefficients gives the difference in the coulombic energy (ΔE_0) in the two media, with a minor contribution from the relatively small change in the solvent composition. ΔE_0 has been calculated⁵ from equation (1)

$$\Delta E_0 = -Z_1 Z_2 e^2 \Delta D / D_1 D_2 r \quad \dots (1)$$

where e is the electronic charge, r the distance of approach between the reacting ions of valencies Z_1 and Z_2 and ΔD the difference between the dielectric constants of the two sets of media. The calculated and the experimental values of ΔE_0 at

$I=0$ for ethanol-water mixtures are 381 and 1104 cal./mole, respectively, taking the value⁴ of r to be 4.6 Å at 30°. The measured activation energy, E , of a reaction involving little or no volume change during the course of the reaction in a medium of dielectric constant, D , and at an ionic strength, I , may be considered to consist of three parts⁶. Thus

$$E = E_0 + E_D + E_I \quad \dots (2)$$

where the subscripts D and I refer to the contribution to the energy of activation of the dielectric constant and ionic strength, respectively and E_0 is the contribution of activation energy due to non-electrostatic interaction. E_D has been calculated from equation (3) of Brønsted-Christiansen-Scatchard⁷.

$$E_D = \frac{Z_1 Z_2 N e^2}{D r} \left(1 + \frac{\partial \ln D}{\partial \ln T} \right) \quad \dots (3)$$

At zero ionic strength, E_I vanishes and the equation (2) becomes

$$E = E_0 + E_D$$

Knowing E_D and E , the experimental activation energy at $I=0$, E_0 , can be determined. The calculated values of E_0 and E_D are given in Table 3 for the isocomposition and isodielectric media used.

The contribution of the ionic atmosphere to the experimental energy of activation has been computed from equation (4) derived by Lamer and Kamner⁸ for low ionic strengths.

$$E_I = -\frac{3NZ_1 Z_2 e^2}{2D} \kappa \left[1 + \frac{\partial \ln D}{\partial \ln T} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{\partial \ln V}{\partial \ln T} \right] \quad \dots (4)$$

The values of $\partial \ln D / \partial \ln T$ and $\partial \ln V / \partial \ln T$ have been obtained from the slopes of the plots of $\ln V$ or $\ln D$ against $\ln T$. The values of D and V (specific volume of the solvent mixture) used at different temperatures have been taken from the literature⁹⁻¹².

 TABLE 3—EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED VALUE OF THE COMPONENTS OF $E/\text{cal. mol}^{-1}$ AND $\log A$ IN DIFFERENT MEDIA AT MID-TEMPERATURE (30°) DIELECTRIC CONSTANT (A in $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)

Solvent	I = 0.02		I = 0.05		I = 0.08		I = 0.11	
	E_I	$\log A_I$	E_I	$\log A_I$	E_I	$\log A_I$	E_I	$\log A_I$
Water	138 (76.2)	0.20 (0.199)	231 (120.4)	0.30 (0.314)	346 (151.5)	0.49 (0.397)	415 (178)	0.57 (0.466)
20% ethanol-water	230 (171.75)	0.24 (0.306)	461 (271.5)	0.49 (0.484)	553 (343.5)	0.52 (0.612)	645 (402.8)	0.63 (0.716)
20% Ethylene glycol-water	203 (160.17)	0.20 (0.275)	346 (253.28)	0.33 (0.438)	530 (320.37)	0.51 (0.553)	553 (375.67)	0.54 (0.649)
Isodielectric ethanol-water, $D = 68.66$	-500 (-342)	0.27 (-0.074)	-851 (-541)	-0.44 (-0.117)	-910 (-684.5)	-0.48 (-0.148)	-1122 (-802.6)	-0.59 (-0.174)
Isodielectric ethylene glycol-water, $D = 68.66$	-92 (-428)	-0.04 (-0.135)	-322 (-676.9)	-0.18 (-0.214)	-443 (-856)	-0.24 (-0.271)	-552 (-1004)	-0.30 (-0.318)
Isodielectric ethanol-water, $D = 50.38$	-780 (-547.5)	-0.33 (-0.120)	-1075 (-865.8)	-0.67 (0.189)	-1305 (-1095)	-0.81 (-0.24)	-1670 (-1284)	-1.04 (-0.281)

Figures in parentheses represent calculated values.

	Solvent					
	Water ($D = 76.75$)	20% ethanol-water ($D = 65.31$)	20% ethylene glycol-water ($D = 71.04$)	Isodielectric ethanol-water ($D = 68.66$)	Isodielectric ethylene glycol-water ($D = 68.66$)	Isodielectric ethanol-water ($D = 50.38$)
E at $I = 0$ (Expt.)	12986	12666	13472	14249	18285	15353
E_D (Calcd.)	-264	-540	-1578	1051	3202	1432
E_0 (Calcd.)	13160	13206	15050	13198	15083	13921
$\log A$ at $I = 0$ (Expt.)	8.21	7.93	8.35	9.07	11.72	9.64
$\log A_D$ (Calcd.)	-0.864	-1.17	-3.34	0	0	0
$\log A_0$ (Calcd.)	9.07	9.10	11.69	9.07	11.72	9.64

TABLE 4—OBSERVED AND CALCULATED VALUES OF $E_{TC} - E_{TD}$ IN CAL. AND $\log A_{TC} - \log A_{TD}$ CORRESPONDING TO MID-TEMPERATURE (30°) DIELECTRIC CONSTANT

Ionic Strength (molar)	Water : Isodielectric ethanol-water D = 68.66		Water : Isodielectric ethanol-water D = 50.38		20% ethanol-water : Isodielectric ethanol-water D = 68.66		20% ethanol-water : Isodielectric ethanol-water D = 50.38		Water : Isodielectric ethylene glycol-water D = 68.66		20% ethylene glycol-water : Isodielectric ethylene glycol-water D = 68.66	
	$(E_{TC} - E_{TD})$	$(\log A_{TC} - \log A_{TD})$	$(E_{TC} - E_{TD})$	$(\log A_{TC} - \log A_{TD})$	$(E_{TC} - E_{TD})$	$(\log A_{TC} - \log A_{TD})$	$(E_{TC} - E_{TD})$	$(\log A_{TC} - \log A_{TD})$	$(E_{TC} - E_{TD})$	$(\log A_{TC} - \log A_{TD})$	$(E_{TC} - E_{TD})$	$(\log A_{TC} - \log A_{TD})$
0	-1353 (-1475)	-0.85 (-0.986)	-2457 (-1856)	-1.43 (-0.986)	-1583 (-1534)	-1.14 (-1.146)	-2687 (-1915)	-1.71 (-1.146)	-5389 (-4407)	-3.51 (-2.99)	-4813 (-4855)	-3.37 (-3.42)
0.02	-715 (-1035)	-0.39 (-0.668)	-1539 (-1416)	-0.90 (-0.668)	-853 (-980)	-0.63 (-0.746)	-1677 (-1362)	-1.14 (0.746)	-5159 (-3978)	-3.27 (-2.67)	-4491 (-4418)	-3.13 (-3.05)
0.05	-307 (-779)	-0.12 (-0.483)	-1151 (-1161)	-0.46 (-0.483)	-307 (-658)	-0.21 (-0.514)	-4836 (-1040)	-0.55 (-0.514)	-4836 (-2723)	-3.03 (-2.49)	-4145 (-4032)	-2.86 (-2.83)
0.08	-97 (-595)	-0.11 (-0.350)	-806 (-976)	-0.13 (-0.35)	-120 (-426)	-0.14 (-0.346)	-829 (-808)	-0.38 (0.346)	-4606 (-3548)	-2.78 (-2.75)	-3846 (-3814)	-2.62 (-2.67)
0.11	+184 (-443)	+0.30 (-0.240)	-372 (-824)	+0.18 (-0.24)	+184 (-235)	+0.08 (-0.208)	-372 (-616)	-0.04 (-0.208)	-4422 (-3400)	-2.64 (-2.24)	-3708 (-3634)	-2.53 (-2.54)

Figures in the parentheses represent calculated values.

In fact, E_I is the difference of activation energies at a certain ionic strength and at zero ionic strength.

The calculated and the observed values of E_I are recorded in Table 3 for ethanol-water and ethylene glycol-water mixtures at four ionic strengths. The experimental values are higher than the calculated values at all ionic strengths for both the solvent systems, but for the lower dielectric constant (ca 50.38) with ethanol-water mixtures, a reverse trend is observed. In spite of the discrepancies between the calculated and the experimental values, the increase and decrease of activation energy in isocomposition and isodielectric media respectively with increase of ionic strength are in the expected direction. For all the solvent systems, the change in the activation energy, resulting from a particular change in ionic strength, is found to be more pronounced in isodielectric media than in isocomposition media. In the case of water-ethanol mixtures, the observed ionic strength decrement of activation energy is larger in the lower isodielectric medium. According to equation (4), the plot of E_I against \sqrt{I} should be a straight line which has been actually observed in the present cases. However, the slopes of the experimental plots are higher than the values expected from equation (4).

The difference in energies of activation ($E_{IC} - E_{ID}$) in isocomposition and isodielectric media for a solvent system, which includes coulombic energy of activation, has been calculated by the modified equation (5) of Amis and Potts¹³.

$$E_{IC} - E_{ID} = \frac{Z_1 Z_2 e^2 N}{D_{IC} J} \left[\left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{3e}{10} \sqrt{\frac{2\pi N I}{10 D_{IC} k T}} \right) \frac{T}{D_{IC}} \frac{dD}{dT} - \frac{\Delta D}{D_{ID} r} \right] \quad \dots (5)$$

where $\Delta D = D_{IC} - D_{ID}$; D_{IC} and D_{ID} are the dielectric constants of the isocomposition and the isodielectric media, respectively. The experimental and calculated values of $E_{IC} - E_{ID}$ in the different media and at various ionic strengths are recorded in Table 4. The dielectric constants and the value of radius, r , used correspond to the mid-temperature, i.e., 30°. There appears to be a large discrepancy in magnitude between the calculated and the experimental values, but for any particular system the discrepancy increases with increasing ionic strength of the solution. Better agreement is however noticed between the observed and the calculated values for 20% ethylene glycol-water mixture.

The pre-exponential factor (A), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) and free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger):

The thermodynamic parameter ΔS^\ddagger can be conceived of as a measure of the differences in the total complexity of the transition state as compared to that of the reactant state. The experimental and the calculated values of A and ΔS^\ddagger at 30° for all the solvent systems and at different ionic strengths are shown in Tables 3 and 5. The values of $\log A_{IC} - \log A_{ID}$ between the isocomposition and the isodielectric media have been calculated by equation (6) of Amis and Cook¹⁴.

$$\log A_{IC} - \log A_{ID} = \frac{Z_1 Z_2 N e^2}{2.303 D^2 R} \left[\frac{1}{r} - \frac{3e}{10} \left(\frac{2\pi N^2 I}{10 D R T} \right)^{1/2} \right] \frac{dD}{dT} \quad \dots (6)$$

where D is the dielectric constant of the isocomposition medium at temperature T . The value of dD/dT is found from the slope of the plot of D against T . The observed and the calculated values of $\log A_{IC} - \log A_{ID}$ are recorded in Table 4. It

TABLE 5—EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED VALUES OF COMPONENTS OF $\Delta S^\ddagger/\text{CAL K}^{-1}$ AND $\Delta G^\ddagger/\text{CAL}$ IN ISOCOMPOSITION AND ISODIELECTRIC MEDIA, CORRESPONDING TO MID-TEMPERATURE (30°) DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS

Solvent	I = 0.02		I = 0.05		I = 0.08		I = 0.11	
	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
Water	0.921 (0.919)	-84 (-202.5)	1.38 (1.45)	-116 (-320.2)	2.25 (1.83)	-20.8 (-405)	2.62 (2.15)	-233 (-474.9)
20% ethanol-water	1.10 (1.40)	-62 (-256.93)	2.25 (2.23)	-133 (-406.3)	2.39 (2.82)	-108 (-513.93)	2.90 (3.30)	-138 (-602.64)
20% ethylene glycol-water	0.921 (1.27)	-55.7 (-226.5)	1.51 (2.02)	-118 (-358)	2.35 (2.55)	-180 (-453)	2.48 (2.99)	-202.3 (-531)
Isodielectric D = 68.66	-1.24 (-0.342)	-72 (-238.46)	-2.02 (-0.540)	-122 (-377)	-2.21 (-0.684)	-147 (-477.0)	-2.71 (-0.802)	-177 (-559.3)
ethanol-water	-0.184 (-0.625)	-42 (-238.3)	-0.83 (-0.989)	-68.3 (-376.8)	-1.10 (1.25)	-110 (-476.6)	-1.38 (-1.467)	-141.2 (-559)
Isodielectric D = 68.66	-1.52 (-0.553)	-73 (-379.44)	-3.08 (-0.874)	-131 (-600)	-3.73 (-1.106)	-173 (-759)	-4.79 (-1.297)	-208 (-890)
ethanol-water								
	Solvent							
	Water (D = 76.75)	20% ethanol-water (D = 65.31)	20% ethylene glycol-water (D = 71.04)	Isodielectric ethanol-water (D = 68.66)	Isodielectric ethylene glycol-water (D = 68.66)	Isodielectric ethanol-water (D = 50.38)		
ΔS^\ddagger at I=0 (Expt.)	-21.0	-16.16	-20.37	-17.2	-4.94	-14.4		
ΔS^\ddagger (Calcd.)	-3.98	-5.42	-15.4	0	0	0		
ΔS^\ddagger (Calcd.)	-17.02	-10.74	-4.97	-17.2	-4.94	-14.4		
ΔG^\ddagger at I=0 (Expt.)	11566	11663	19562	11659	19672	19635		
ΔG^\ddagger (Calcd.)	942.7	1105.00	3095	1051.00	3202	1432.5		
ΔG^\ddagger (Calcd.)	10623.3	10558	16467	10608	16470	18202.5		

is seen from the table that there is great disagreement, which is largely dependent on the ionic strength, between the observed and the calculated values. The calculated and the observed values of $\log A_{IC} - \log A_{ID}$ for 20% ethanol-water and isodielectric ethanol-water medium ($D=50.38$), though high at zero ionic strength, become progressively smaller with the increase of ionic strength. In the case of the isocomposition media, water and 20% ethylene glycol-water, and isodielectric ($D=68.66$) ethylene glycol-water solvents, the calculated and the observed values of $\log A_{IC} - \log A_{ID}$ are however in satisfactory agreement, particularly for 20% ethylene glycol-water and isodielectric ($D=68.66$) ethylene glycol-water system.

The entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) is also made up of three contributions⁶.

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = \Delta S_o^\ddagger + \Delta S_D^\ddagger + \Delta S_I^\ddagger \quad \dots (7)$$

where the subscripts have the same meanings as in equation (2). ΔS_D^\ddagger has been calculated from equation (8).

$$\Delta S_D^\ddagger = \frac{NZ_1Z_2e^2}{DT} \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\partial \ln D}{\partial \ln T} \right) \quad \dots (8)$$

Thus by knowing ΔS_D^\ddagger and ΔS_I^\ddagger which is zero at $I=0$, the value of ΔS_o^\ddagger can be calculated.

Equation (9) has been used to calculate the contribution of the ionic atmosphere (ΔS_I^\ddagger) to the ΔS^\ddagger .

$$\Delta S_I^\ddagger = -\frac{3}{2} \frac{NZ_1Z_2e^2}{DT} \kappa \left[\frac{1}{3} + \frac{\partial \ln D}{\partial \ln T} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{\partial \ln V}{\partial \ln T} \right] \quad \dots (9)$$

The values of ΔS_D^\ddagger , ΔS_o^\ddagger , and ΔS_I^\ddagger are recorded in Table 5. Considerable disagreement between the experimental and the calculated values is observed, but the change is in the expected direction. In the case of water, however, the observed and the calculated values are in fairly good agreement.

Like ΔS^\ddagger , $\log A$ may also be thought of as consisting of three contributions, $\log A_o$, $\log A_D$, $\log A_I$. $\log A_I$ is given by equation (10).

$$\log A_I = \frac{\Delta S_I^\ddagger}{2.303R} \quad \dots (10)$$

The values of $\log A_o$, $\log A_D$ and $\log A_I$ in different solvent systems are shown in Table 3. Discrepancies between the observed and the calculated values are notable, except in the case with water as the medium for which excellent agreement is obtained.

The free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) also consists of three components given by equation (11).

$$\Delta G^\ddagger = \Delta G_o^\ddagger + \Delta G_D^\ddagger + \Delta G_I^\ddagger \quad \dots (11)$$

ΔG_D^\ddagger and ΔG_I^\ddagger have been computed from equations (12) and (13)

$$\Delta G_D^\ddagger = Z_1Z_2Ne^2/Dr \quad \dots (12)$$

$$\Delta G_I^\ddagger = -Z_1Z_2Ne^2 \kappa/D \quad \dots (13)$$

ΔG_o^\ddagger has been obtained by subtracting ΔG_D^\ddagger from ΔG^\ddagger at $I=0$. The values of ΔG^\ddagger and ΔG_I^\ddagger for all the solvent systems at different ionic strengths and the calculated values of ΔG_D^\ddagger and ΔG_o^\ddagger are recorded in Table 5. The experimental and the

calculated values are of the same sign, but there are wide discrepancies in the magnitude for all the solvent systems and at all the ionic strengths.

Non-electrostatic effects :

The mutual potential energy between the reacting particles at a distance r consists of electrostatic potential energy, $\phi_s(r)$, and non-electrostatic potential energy, $\phi_1(r)$, and on this basis, Amis and Jaffe¹⁵ arrived at equations (14), (15) and (16).

$$\text{At } I=0, \phi_2(r) = \frac{Z_1Z_2e^2}{Dr} \quad \dots (14)$$

$$a_T = \frac{d \ln k}{d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right) D} = - \frac{1}{k} \left[\phi_1(r) + \frac{Z_1Z_2e^2}{Dr} \right] \quad \dots (15)$$

$$a_D = \frac{d \ln k}{d \left(\frac{1}{D} \right) T} = - \frac{Z_1Z_2e^2}{kTr} \quad \dots (16)$$

The values for $\phi_1(r)$, $\phi_2(r)$, a_T and a_D for isodielectric media ($D=68.66$) comprising glycol-water and ethanol-water have been calculated using the above equations and are recorded in Table 6.

TABLE 6—CALCULATED VALUES OF NON-ELECTROSTATIC, $\phi_1(r)$ AND ELECTROSTATIC POTENTIAL, $\phi_2(r)$ CORRESPONDING TO ISODIELECTRIC ETHANOL-WATER AND ETHYLENE GLYCOL-WATER MIXTURES AT MIDD-TEMPERATURE, 30°

Solvent	a_T	a_D	$\phi_1(r)$ erg $\times 10^{12}$	$\phi_2(r)$ erg $\times 10^{12}$	$\phi_1(r)/\phi_2(r)$
Ethanol-water ($D=68.66$)	-7235	-119	0.925	0.729	12.68
Ethanol-water ($D=50.38$)	-7641	-119	0.955	0.994	9.6
Ethylene glycol-water ($D=68.66$)	-8940	-364.9	1.0115	2.222	4.55

Correlation of activation parameters :

It will be seen from Table 2 that the activation energies (at zero ionic strength) for glycol-water solvent system monotonically increase with increase in the proportion of the organic component in the solvent mixtures, i.e. with decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium. This is quite expected in view of the fact that the two reacting ions are of like charge. For ethanol-water system, however, the energy of activation remains reasonably unchanged (rather showing a flat minimum around 10% ethanol) upto about 20% ethanol. The decrease in dielectric constant is thus compensated for by large solvation in the aquo-organic mixtures in this region. Since the doubly charged transition state contains both hydrophilic and hydrophobic parts, the presence of water and an organic solvent in optimum proportion is expected to lead to stronger solvation and hence greater stabilisation of the activated complex than in mixtures of other compositions. A similar observation was found for the alkaline hydrolysis of acetylmandelate ion¹⁶, where a distinct minimum for the activation energy was found with 20% ethanol-water medium.

The activation energy, E_0 , in isodielectric media is higher than in isocomposition media, as expected for a reaction between two ions of like charge. For the same dielectric constant (68.66), the E_0 value is much higher for glycolic than for ethanolic mixture. The transition state thus appears to be more solvated (relative to the reacting ions) in ethanolic than in glycolic medium. This is also substantiated by the more negative value of ΔS^\ddagger for the ethanol-water medium. ΔG^\ddagger for the isodielectric (68.66) ethanol-water has a much lower positive value than for the corresponding isodielectric glycol-water medium. Thus there seems to be rather a poor compensation between ΔH^\ddagger and $T\Delta S^\ddagger$. Structural differences between the two solvent media are expected to be largely involved in the observed ΔS^\ddagger values. It may be noted that the activation parameters for two sets of isodielectric media at zero ionic strength are directly comparable, unlike the corresponding values for isocomposition media.

The much larger value (12.68) of the ratio $\phi_1(r)/\phi_2(r)$ for ethanol-water compared to that (4.56) for glycol-water (Table 6) indicates that the nonelectrostatic effect predominates in the former medium. This further substantiates that the transition state is more solvated in ethanol-water than in glycol-water media, as indicated by the values of activation energy as well as the entropy of activation.

The discrepancies between the experimental and the calculated values for E_I and ΔS^\ddagger (Tables 3 and 5) are found to be quite pronounced for the isodielectric ethanol-water media with lower D (~ 50), and probably arise from ion association, the true ionic strength being less than the stoichiometric value. The discrepancies regarding $E_{IO} - E_{ID}$ values have been referred to in an earlier section.

The large differences between the experimental and the calculated values for the various components of the activation parameters obviously arise from the fact that the equations used to calculate

the different quantities do not take into account all the factors involved, as well as from the inadequacy of the model used for deducing the respective equations.

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